

Exploring Equity in Pedestrian Traffic Safety with Open Source Data: A Census Tract Level Study in Nevada

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Abstract

In recent years, equity issues have moved to the forefront of traffic safety studies, and developing a data-driven approach is critical to statistically portray traffic safety disparity related to socioeconomic profiles (e.g., race, income, and education). However, without effective and efficient tools and methodologies, exploring equity in traffic safety can require intensive effort in data collection and processing, leading to budgetary and resource burdens for transportation agencies. In this study, an analysis of pedestrian safety disparity across various socioeconomic groups in Nevada is presented mainly using open-source data, which aims to help transportation agencies identify equity issues at a minimal data collection cost. For each census tract, socioeconomic profiles and crash data are integrated, and a descriptive pattern study was conducted to reveal the pattern of safety disparities. The results indicate safety disparities among different socioeconomic groups and can facilitate the development of countermeasures and transportation agencies' future funding allocation.

Key Words: Equity; pedestrian safety; open source data; census tract

1. Background and Introduction

Equity is the bedrock of American democracy, and diversity is one of the nation's greatest strengths. From a broad perspective, transportation equity refers to fairness and impartiality in providing and distributing transportation services and benefits to all members of society, regardless of their race, ethnicity, income, or location. Equity in transportation can be viewed from two different angles: horizontal equity, which aims to treat people with similar needs and abilities equally, and vertical equity, which seeks to allocate a greater share of resources to disadvantaged groups (Litman 2021). Furthermore, equity can be interpreted as the need to distribute resources to satisfy the most basic accessibility needs (Talen 1998), maximize benefits for the most disadvantaged groups (Palmateer and Levinson 2017), allocate resources based on the share of the user population (Creutzig et al. 2020), or allocate resources proportionally to user payments, with those who pay more receiving more services (Levinson 2010).

Despite being a nation founded on principles of equality, the United States still struggles with persistent racial and ethnic disparities that extend to traffic safety and access. In 2020, motor vehicle crashes resulted in the death of 38824 people on US roadways, with people of color experiencing a disproportional burden of fatalities (Raifman and Choma 2022). Researchers also found that drivers' socioeconomic characteristics, including race, income, and education, can impact their likelihood of being at fault in a crash (Sagar et al. 2021). Additionally, transportation policies, such as transportation funding allocation and infrastructure investment, may favor certain communities or regions over others, leading to unequal access to transportation and unequal distribution of transportation benefits (Ryan et al. 2021). The impact of transportation inequalities can extend to disparities in the economy, education quality, job opportunities, and health outcomes (Cain and Jones 2008). Those adverse situations mentioned above interact with and influence each other,

creating a vicious cycle that reinforces systemic inequality and negatively impacts marginalized groups, leading to increased social fragmentation.

At the same time, the government has been actively pursuing strategies to advance equity for all by promoting fairness and inclusivity in society. For example, the white house signed five Executive Orders that aim at improving equity. These include Executive Order 13985— Advancing Racial Equity and Support for Underserved Communities Through the Federal Government(Executive Order 13985 2021). Executive Order 13988—Preventing and Combating Discrimination on the Basis of Gender Identity or Sexual Orientation (Executive Order 13988 2021), and Executive Order 14035—Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in the Federal Workforce(Executive Order 14035 2021). In addition, the US Department of Transportation has identified equity as one of its research priorities in their five-year Strategic Plan from 2022 to 2026 (U.S. Department of Transportation 2022). Efforts to improve equity in transportation have also been underway at the state, local, and organizational levels. State agencies, non-profit organizations, and transportation agencies have implemented equity-focused programs that aim to improve equity in transportation through coordination, evaluation, implementation, mapping, and planning (Van Dort et al. 2019).

1.1 Research gaps and research objective

Despite increased efforts to address equity in transportation, significant gaps still exist in the field, particularly with regard to traffic safety. While transportation access equity has been extensively studied, traffic safety receives less attention despite being responsible for thousands of deaths annually. Additionally, significant gaps exist in studying traffic equity at a granular level below the state level. While this is feasible in large cities like New York, San Francisco, and Los Angeles, conducting granular equity studies is much more challenging in small cities due to limited data availability. This gap needs to be addressed to better understand the specific traffic safety challenges faced by communities at the local level and to develop targeted solutions that address these challenges. This paper aims to address the above-mentioned gaps by examining the following questions:

1. Do socioeconomically disadvantaged groups experience safety disparity in transportation?
2. What groups experience the most significant disparity?
3. How to study the above questions at the tract level

To answer the questions, this research explores safety equity in transportation among groups of different socioeconomic features in Washoe County, Nevada. Socioeconomic data is obtained from ACS five-year survey, and crash data from 2016 to 2020 is obtained from NDOT Geohub website. Census tract is the minimum studying unit in geometry, and all data are processed and grouped at the tract level. Selected socioeconomic variables include poverty, education, disability, age, income, internet coverage, health insurance coverage, housing status, gender, and race. Crashes are divided into motorized and non-motorized crashes due to location-based crash data. A correlation study and descriptive analysis between socioeconomic variables and the crash rate are conducted to find a general pattern in safety disparity. The result shows apparent safety disparities for socioeconomically disadvantaged groups and colored race groups. Moreover, the result of this study indicates the need to consider how funding methods can address the disparities.

2. Literature review

Transportation equity has been explored from different perspectives: accessibility, investment, cost/congestion burden, pollution, and crashes. In research that used transportation accessibility equity as a research target, traditional public transit tools, electronic charging stations, scooters, and bike lanes are explorable factors. Liu studied public transit delays and disruptions in Toronto and found that equity-seeking groups were more vulnerable to disruptions or had less resiliency than the general population theoretically (Sagar et al. 2021). In California, spatial disparities of electric vehicle charging stations were validated for low-income areas with low car ownership and a median age of 25-24 population (Roy and Law 2022). The spatial accessibility of scooter and bike services

is investigated among disadvantaged communities in Texas and revealed that areas with a higher proportion of Black residents were less likely to have access to both bikes and scooters (Aman et al. 2021).

Disparities in crash outcomes were also explored and verified. The disparities in crash outcomes in different driver features were found at the state level in Alabama and Kentucky. In Alabama, drivers involving no seatbelt usage, driving under influence (DUI), unemployed drivers, young drivers, distracted driving, and African American drivers are experiencing disparity in crash outcomes (Adanu et al. 2017). In Kentucky, socioeconomic features such as income, poverty level, employment, age, gender, rurality, and the number of traffic-related convictions of a driver's zip code influence their likelihood of being at fault in a two-unit crash (Sagar et al. 2021). At the country level, Hasselberg investigated socioeconomic differences in road traffic injuries among Swedish children and adolescents in Swedish and found that injury-risk differentials increase when young people use motorized vehicles (Hasselberg 2001). In the US, travel is less risky for white people than for people of most other race-ethnicity groups (Raifman and Choma 2022). American Indian/Alaskan Native persons and black persons experienced the highest traffic death rate among all races (Governors Highway Safety Association 2021).

Transportation equity studies face significant challenges in obtaining detailed personal information through open sources due to privacy considerations. A surrogate way is to use the geographically aggregated information to represent personal characteristics within a given area, using the geographic unit as the study target. One such source of geographically aggregated data is the American Community Survey (ACS), which collects and publishes socioeconomic information at the census tract level each year. The census tract is therefore an ideal substitute for personal information in transportation equity studies (U.S. Census Bureau, 2018). Although many current studies have identified disparities in transportation from different approaches, most have been limited to large geographic resolutions, such as country-wide and statewide analyses. There is a lack of traffic safety equity studies that use smaller geographic resolutions. This may be partly due to the greater data availability for large geographic areas, making large-scale studies more achievable. However, due to limited data availability, performing granular analyses of transportation equity is more difficult. Moreover, many existing studies have used data that are not open to the public, making it challenging to apply their methodologies in other areas. It is essential to use data that are universally accessible to evaluate equity without intensive costs and resources. Thus, there is a need for more open-access data sources to improve the accuracy and generalizability of transportation equity studies.

3. Methodology

The purpose of this study is to explore traffic safety equity by analyzing the distribution of crashes across various socioeconomic and demographic groups in different modes. To achieve this, an observational study is presented, utilizing data collected from Washoe County, Nevada. The dataset comprises socioeconomic and demographic information as well as traffic crash data, all of which were obtained from open public sources. Variable definition and descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1 and Table 2, followed by a Pearson correlation analysis (Table 3) to examine the relationship between variables. Finally, a disparity pattern analysis is performed to identify any discernible patterns in the data.

3.1 Data

The American Community Survey (ACS) is a comprehensive survey conducted by the United States Census Bureau that gathers important social, economic, and demographic information on the country's population. Specifically, the ACS five-year survey provides average socioeconomic information in small geographic units over a five-year period (U.S. Census Bureau 2018). It has been widely used by government agencies, businesses, non-profit organizations, researchers and individuals to make informed decisions or conduct programs due to its well-established development, broad coverage and easy accessibility. By leveraging open-source data such as ACS,

local organizations and small research groups with limited budgets or access to private data sources can significantly reduce costs and save resources. In this research, several socioeconomic variables of 132 census tracts in Washoe County in Nevada are collected from the ACS five-year survey. The used socioeconomic variables include education, housing, income, disability, poverty, health insurance, internet coverage, race, gender and age. Nevada Department of Transportation (NDOT) offers open access to crash data on its website, providing a range of essential information on crashes such as crash severity (KABCO), location, driver age, crash type, and travel mode (“NDOT GeoHub” 2023). In this research, a total of 1328 fatal (K), incapability (A) crashes, and non-incapability (B) crashes between 2016 to 2020 are used for non-motorized crashes, a total of 3172 fatal (K), incapability (A), and non-incapability (B) crashes between 2016 to 2020 are used for motorized crashes. Even if fatal (K) and incapability (A) crashes are preferable crash types, however, non-incapability (B) crashes are include due to a small sample size of K and A crashes.

The five-year crash data are divided and summarized at the tract level to match the socioeconomic data from the ACS five-year survey. In the aggregation process, many crashes overlap with the census tract boundary when assigning them due to the census tract boundary usually overlapping with roadway networks, thus making it hard to decide which tract should be assigned. To address this, crashes are categorized into two groups based on their proximity to the census tract boundary: those within 100 meters and those outside 100 meters. A buffer of 100 meters is considered wide enough to incorporate any boundary-overlapping roadways and reasonably narrow not to let the buffer extend too much to other census tracts. Then crashes within 100 meters of the census tract boundary were evenly distributed to the neighboring tracts. To compute the total crash frequency for each tract, the number of averaged boundary crashes was added to the number of inside crashes.

Table 1 gives a verbal description for each socioeconomic variable that is possibly hard to understand, the data coverage period is from 2016 to 2020, and the data resolution is census tract. Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics of all variables used in this study, including mean, median, range, maximum, minimum, standard deviations, and percentile values. All variables are aggregated at the tract level, with a total of 132 tracts. Crashes are measured by crash frequency, while socioeconomic variables and demographic variables are measured by percentage, except for mean income and age, which are represented by dollar and year. For variables using rate as a unit, disability, gender, Percent American Indian and Alaska Native, and Percent Black or African American have relatively centralized distributions compared to other variables, with standard deviations of 4.9, 1.9, 3.0, and 4.7, respectively. House rent status has the highest dispersion, with a range of 98 percent and a standard deviation of 28.3. Followed by percent white (16.6), percent Hispanic or Latino (15.1), and commute time over 30 minutes (12.7).

Table 1: Socioeconomic variable description

Variables	Description
Poverty(%)	Population percentage below poverty level
25+ High School Degree(%)	Rate of high school degree for population who is above 25 years old
25+ Bachelor Degree(%)	Rate of bachelor degree for population who is above 25 years old
Disability(%)	Population disability rate including: vision difficulty, cognitive difficulty, ambulatory difficulty, self-care difficulty, independent living difficulty
House by Owner(%)	Rate of population who's living house is self-owned
House by Rent(%)	Rate of population who's living house is rented
Insurance Coverage(%)	Health insurance coverage rate
Internet Coverage(%)	Internet coverage rage including:dial-up,cable, fiber optic, or DSL, satellite internet service
Mean Age(year)	Average age of all population
Mean Income(\$)	Mean income of all population
Commute 30min+(%)	Percentage of commuting time over 30 minutes among people who commuting to work

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for variables

Category	Variables	Mean	Median	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Deviation	Percentiles		
								25	50	75
Crash	Motorized Crash(K&A&B)	24.0	17.3	182.0	0.5	182.5	25.1	8.5	17.3	29.1
	Non-motorized Crash(K&A&B)	9.8	6.5	68.5	0.0	68.5	10.5	3.5	6.5	12.0
Socioeconomic	Poverty(%)	11.6	9.7	55.8	0.4	56.2	9.6	4.5	9.7	16.2
	25+ High School Degree(%)	23.6	24.5	38.7	4.0	42.7	8.8	17.1	24.5	30.8
	25+ Bachelor Degree(%)	19.9	19.4	44.1	2.2	46.3	9.4	12.7	19.4	26.3
	Disability(%)	12.4	12.0	29.3	3.1	32.4	4.9	8.9	12.0	15.2
	House by Owner(%)	56.4	63.0	98.0	2.0	100.0	28.3	31.3	63.0	81.0
	House by Rent(%)	43.6	37.0	98.0	0.0	98.0	28.3	19.0	37.0	68.8
	Insurance Coverage(%)	90.0	91.5	31.2	68.8	100.0	7.0	84.8	91.5	95.6
	Internet Coverage(%)	87.2	89.5	45.0	55.0	100.0	9.4	81.3	89.5	95.0
	Mean Age(year)	39.2	38.3	42.0	16.2	58.3	6.3	34.6	38.3	43.8
	Mean Income(\$)	81941.3	80311.3	122502.5	23965.0	146467.5	27094.5	60301.3	80311.3	103614.4
	Commute 30min+(%)	26.3	23.9	74.9	3.8	78.7	12.7	17.3	23.9	32.8
	Demographic	male(%)	50.6	50.3	32.0	36.8	68.8	4.7	47.8	50.3
female(%)		49.4	49.7	32.0	31.2	63.2	4.7	46.5	49.7	52.2
Percent Hispanic or Latino(%)		24.3	19.4	60.7	4.5	65.2	15.1	12.5	19.4	35.1
Percent White alone, not Hispanic or Latino(%)		60.1	63.0	66.0	20.6	86.6	16.6	47.5	63.0	72.7
Percent Black or African American alone, not Hispanic or Latino(%)		2.5	1.9	9.5	0.2	9.7	2.0	1.0	1.9	3.6
Percent American Indian and Alaska Native alone, not Hispanic or Latino(%)		1.0	0.8	19.0	0.1	19.1	1.9	0.5	0.8	0.9
Percent Asian alone, not Hispanic or Latino(%)		5.7	5.5	14.2	0.7	14.9	3.0	3.3	5.5	7.4

3.2 Correlation Study

A Pearson correlation study is conducted to investigate the correlation index among variables, which is illustrated in Table 3 and Table 4. Table 3 shows the variable correlations between motorized crashes and non-motorized crashes. Overall, the positive and negative correlation patterns are similar for both motorized crashes and non-motorized crashes except for mean age and percent Asian alone. Variables that are positively correlated with crashes include poverty, disability, house by rent, male, Percent Hispanic or Latino, Percent Black or African American, Percent American Indian and Alaska Native. Variables that are negatively correlated with crashes include Bachelor's Degree, Insurance Coverage, Internet Coverage, Mean Income, Commute 30min+, and Percent White. In Table 4, several variables were found to be highly correlated, with a correlation index greater than 0.7. For instance, mean income was negatively correlated with poverty (-0.704), while it was positively correlated with house by rent (0.797), internet coverage (0.724), and white population (0.717). In contrast, mean income was negatively correlated with black population (-0.735). House by rent was positively correlated with the black population (0.783). It is important to note that even though some variables exhibit high correlations, they were not removed from the analysis. A correlation coefficient of 0.7 still leaves 0.3 of the difference unexplained. Additionally, the local distribution of crashes across different socioeconomic levels may differ, and thus they may contribute differently to the overall pattern of disparities observed. Variable pairs with a correlation coefficient of 1, such as house by rent/house by owner and male/female, were removed from the analysis because they are perfect opposites of each other.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Index between variables and travel modes

Variable/Travel Mode	Motorized Crash(K&A&B)	Non-motorized Crash(K&A&B)
Poverty(%)	0.275	0.275
25+ Bachelor Degree(%)	-0.239	-0.239
Disability(%)	0.368	0.368
House by Rent(%)	0.285	0.285
Insurance Coverage(%)	-0.373	-0.373
Internet Coverage(%)	-0.407	-0.407
Mean Age(year)	0.006	0.006
Mean Income(\$)	-0.333	-0.333
Commute 30min+(%)	-0.068	-0.068
Male(%)	0.310	0.310
Percent Hispanic or Latino(%)	0.222	0.222
Percent White(%)	-0.297	-0.297
Percent Black or African American (%)	0.372	0.372
Percent American Indian and Alaska Native(%)	0.456	0.456
Percent Asian(%)	-0.017	-0.017

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Index among variables

Variable/Variable	Poverty (%)	25+ Bachelor Degree(%)	Disability(%)	House by Rent(%)	Insurance Coverage (%)	Internet Coverage(%)	Mean Age(year)	Mean Income (\$)	Commute 30min+(%)	Male(%)	Percent Hispanic or Latino(%)	Percent White(%)	Percent Black or African American (%)	American Indian and Alaska Native(%)	Percent Asian (%)
Poverty(%)	1	-0.396	0.316	0.659	-0.553	-0.577	-0.360	-0.704	-0.137	0.300	0.426	-0.491	0.600	0.128	0.004
25+ Bachelor Degree(%)	-0.396	1	-0.441	-0.324	0.503	0.471	0.361	0.634	-0.097	-0.148	-0.718	0.696	-0.400	-0.203	0.176
Disability(%)	0.316	-0.441	1	0.388	-0.364	-0.529	0.165	-0.531	-0.003	0.305	0.294	-0.334	0.407	0.114	-0.022
House by Rent(%)	0.659	-0.324	0.388	1.000	-0.600	-0.651	-0.418	-0.797	-0.248	0.138	0.449	-0.576	0.783	0.054	0.235
Insurance Coverage(%)	-0.553	0.503	-0.364	-0.600	1	0.550	0.300	0.686	0.076	-0.105	-0.595	0.598	-0.469	-0.111	0.065
Internet Coverage(%)	-0.577	0.471	-0.529	-0.651	0.550	1	0.207	0.724	0.178	-0.355	-0.523	0.572	-0.598	-0.172	0.020
Mean Age(year)	-0.360	0.361	0.165	-0.418	0.300	0.207	1	0.429	0.016	-0.025	-0.564	0.637	-0.401	-0.039	-0.287
Mean Income(\$)	-0.704	0.634	-0.531	-0.797	0.686	0.724	0.429	1	0.169	-0.155	-0.640	0.717	-0.735	-0.146	-0.026
Commute 30min+(%)	-0.137	-0.097	-0.003	-0.248	0.076	0.178	0.016	0.169	1	0.172	-0.122	0.161	-0.099	0.156	-0.320
Male(%)	0.300	-0.148	0.305	0.138	-0.105	-0.355	-0.025	-0.155	0.172	1	0.077	-0.092	0.208	0.079	-0.132
Percent Hispanic or Latino(%)	0.426	-0.718	0.294	0.449	-0.595	-0.523	-0.564	-0.640	-0.122	0.077	1	-0.955	0.424	0.093	-0.032
Percent White alone	-0.491	0.696	-0.334	-0.576	0.598	0.572	0.637	0.717	0.161	-0.092	-0.955	1	-0.602	-0.188	-0.187
Percent Black or African American (%)	0.600	-0.400	0.407	0.783	-0.469	-0.598	-0.401	-0.735	-0.099	0.208	0.424	-0.602	1	0.128	0.260
Percent American Indian and Alaska	0.128	-0.203	0.114	0.054	-0.111	-0.172	-0.039	-0.146	0.156	0.079	0.093	-0.188	0.128	1	-0.134
Percent Asian(%)	0.004	0.176	-0.022	0.235	0.065	0.020	-0.287	-0.026	-0.320	-0.132	-0.032	-0.187	0.260	-0.134	1

4. Disparity Pattern Analysis

The primary objective of this study is to investigate whether socioeconomically disadvantaged groups experience disparities in traffic safety. While Pearson correlation indexes have been calculated among variables, these indexes only provide an overall correlation of all datasets. When the values of each variable are highly clustered in a certain range, it is difficult to differentiate between the most advantaged and disadvantaged groups. To better visualize the differences, Census tracts are grouped based on range percentiles of socioeconomic variables, including Most Advantaged Group (MAG), Advantaged Group (AG), Most Disadvantaged Group (MDG), and Disadvantaged Group (DG). MAG includes variable values in the zero to 25th percentile range, AG includes variable values in the 25th to 50th percentile range, MDG includes variable values in the 50th to 75th percentile range, and DG includes variable values in the 75th to 100th percentile range. For demographic variables, census tracts are ranked and grouped from low population rate to high population rate, resulting in four groups: Highest Group (H1), High Group (H2), Low Group (L1), and Lowest Group (L2). Then Box plots are used as a preferred method to better visualize the variations among different socioeconomic strata.

Figure 1a: Motorized crashes(K&A&B) and socioeconomic variable, in each box, ‘×’ represents the mean value, and the solid line indicates the median value.

Figure 1b: Motorized crashes(K&A&B) and demographic variable, in each box, ‘x’ represents the mean value, and the solid line indicates the median value.

Figure 2a: Non-motorized crashes(K&A&B) and socioeconomic variable, in each box, 'x' represents the mean value, and the solid line indicates the median value.

Figure 2b: Non-motorized crashes(K&A&B) and demographic variable, in each box, ‘x’ represents the mean value, and the solid line indicates the median value.

4.1 Motorized Crashes

Figure 1a and Figure 1b illustrate the distribution of Motorized crashes across different socioeconomic and demographic groups. In Figure 1a, apparent differences between MAG and MDG were observed for poverty, bachelor's degree, disability, house by rent, internet coverage, insurance coverage and mean income. What should be noted is that the rate of commute time more than 30 minutes shows a reverse pattern with other variables. Census tracts with a higher percentage of long commute time are less likely to have crashes than census tracts with a low percentage of long commute time. In terms of demographics shown in Figure 1b, evident disparities between the lowest percentage group and the highest percentage group were observed for the Hispanic population, Black population, American Indian population, and male population groups (all populations are aggregated and represented by census tract percentage), while an obvious advantaged situation is observed with the white population. The disparity is not apparent when using the Asian population and gender as variables.

4.2 Non-Motorized Crashes

Figures 2a and 2b display the distribution of non-motorized crashes across socioeconomic and demographic groups, with a line connecting the mean crashes of each group. The results demonstrate a clear and significant disparity in traffic crashes between different groups. In Figure 2a, variables such as poverty, bachelor's degree, disability, living house by rent, insurance coverage, and internet coverage show a significant difference between the MAG and MDG. Similar to Motorized crashes, a reverse pattern is observed with long commuting time, where groups with lower rates of long commuting time experience more crashes. In Figure 2b, apparent disparities were observed for the Hispanic or Latino population, Black population, and American Indian population, while an advantaged situation is observed for the white population. Groups with higher male percentages show a subtle trend of experiencing more non-motorized crashes. Non-motorized crashes do not exhibit a clear pattern for the Asian population and mean age variables.

5. Discussion

In the pattern analysis study, despite some minor fluctuations among groups for several variables, the overall pattern remains evident, and the difference between MAG and MDG remains significant. Generally, socioeconomic and demographic variables exhibit similar patterns for both motorized crashes and non-motorized crashes. In the study area, disparities in traffic safety exist for socioeconomically disadvantaged groups, including tracts with high poverty rate, low bachelor's degree rate, high rent rate in living houses, low income, low insurance coverage rate, and low internet coverage rates. Apparent disparities were also observed for the Hispanic or Latino, Black, and American Indian populations, and tracts with a high male population are more likely to experience crashes. In terms of mean age and Asian population, no clear pattern is observed in both travel modes.

A notable situation was observed among groups when using the 30-minute commute time rate as a variable. It appears that tracts with lower rates of long commute time are both more likely to have motorized crashes and non-motorized crashes. By examining the box plot, it can be seen that the mean value of each box is higher than its median value. Referring to the variable range, the range of commute time 30 min+ is [3.8,78.7], with percentile values of 17.3%,23.9%, and 32.8% for the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles. When comparing the maximum value of 78.6% with the 75th percentile value of 32.8%, and the mean and median in the box plot, it is evident that some tracts have extremely high crashes, as verified by the histogram of the crash frequency distribution in Figure 3. The tail on the right side of the histogram may contribute to a larger mean value than the median value. The low crash for the higher rate of long commute time may be due to the use of more public transit, which may be more time-consuming but leads to lower crash injuries. This is one of the possible explanations, but it still needs further study. Although the mean value shows an obvious pattern, the median value exhibits more fluctuations, and the pattern is much less pronounced.

By referring to the Pearson correlation index and the box plot, non-motorized crashes have higher correlation indexes than motorized crashes with variables in general, and the difference between MAG and MDG in the box plots is more divergent for non-motorized crashes, too. One possible explanation is that the crash data used in this study is crash location-based rather than the drivers' or pedestrians' resident location. A driver may experience a crash in location B while living far in another place B. Therefore, the local socioeconomic information may not truly indicate the feature of the drive. On the other hand, driving a car usually has much more mobility than walking or biking. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that pedestrians or bike riders are more likely than drivers to live in the neighborhood of the crash location. Moreover, the proportion of Black populations is very low in the study region, with a range of [0.2%,9.7%], but results still show apparent disparity for the Black population. Meanwhile, the Black population rate has 0.7 above correlation indexes with mean income, house by rent. The apparent disparity in the population may be a comprehensive result of these variables.

Figure 3: Crash histogram for Motorized Crash(K&A&B) and Non-motorized Crash(K&A&B)

6.1 Limitation

There are several limitations of this study, which would be the future extensions of the research effort:

- The crash data used in this study are located by the crash location rather than the original resident place of drivers or pedestrians. It is often the case that the crash location may not

always correspond to the individuals' resident location. As a result, the socioeconomic information associated with the crash location may not always reflect the accurate crash distribution. If the individual's zip code is attainable will make the study more accurate.

- This is an exploratory study and the crash data sample in Washoe County is small. And the socioeconomic feature and demographic composition also differ among areas. Therefore, a pattern observed in a case study can not fully reflect the crash distribution in the state or countrywide.
- This study used crash frequency as the primary safety measurement. However, the crash rate is not used due to a limitation in data and methodology challenges associated with exposure measurement for pedestrians. A future study could be conducted that utilizes crash rate as the primary safety measurement and compare its findings with those obtained through crash frequency. Such a study would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the safety profile of the study area.
- The minimum study unit in this research is the census tract. At this level, crash counts and socioeconomic and demographic information are aggregated to provide a surrogate representation of individuals due to a big data gap in attaining personal information. However, such representation only offers an indirect pattern of the crash distribution and can not represent the crash distribution directly.
- This study utilized mean age as a variable to indicate the age range among census tracts, with a range of [16.2,58.3] and a standard deviation of 6.3. However, the results did not reveal a clear disparity pattern for the mean age variable. Using mean age averages the younger and older age groups, leading to a more centered age distribution closer to the median. However, reports indicate that individuals between age of 15-24 and 75 above have the highest death rates in traffic crashes ("Motor Vehicle" n.d.). Therefore, future studies should focus on young and old individuals to better understand the safety dynamics for these populations when more data are available.

6. Conclusion

By fully utilizing open-source data, this study used a cost-efficiently way to uncover the disproportional crash distribution between motorized and non-motorized travel across various socioeconomic and demographic groups in Washoe County, Nevada. The analysis revealed that most socioeconomically disadvantaged groups and colored race groups are positively related to crashes, while most socioeconomically advantaged groups and white population are negatively related to crashes. Further study is needed on the Black race population due to the low population coverage rate, on the commute time to find the fact why groups with short commute time experience higher crashes, and on the age variable to focus more on young and old drivers. Overall, the study's findings highlight the need for funding methods that can effectively address the disparities in crash risk observed among different socioeconomic and demographic groups. This study will contribute to a better understanding of traffic safety disparities and inform policies aimed at promoting equitable access to safe transportation.

Author Contributions

The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: Seri Park and Suoyao Feng; data collection: Suoyao Feng; analysis and interpretation of results: Suoyao Feng; draft manuscript preparation: Suoyao Feng and Seri Park. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

References

- Adanu, E. K., Smith, R., Powell, L., and Jones, S. 2017. Multilevel analysis of the role of human factors in regional disparities in crash outcomes. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*. 109, 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2017.09.022>.
- Aman, J. J. C., Zakhem, M., and Smith-Colin, J. 2021. Towards Equity in Micromobility: Spatial Analysis of Access to Bikes and Scooters amongst Disadvantaged Populations. *Sustainability*. 13, 11856. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111856>.
- An Analysis of Traffic Fatalities by Race and Ethnicity. 2021. Governors Highway Safety Association.
- Cain, A., and Jones, P. M. 2008. Does Urban Road Pricing Cause Hardship to Low-Income Car Drivers? An Affordability-Based Approach, *Transportation Research Record*, SAGE Publications Inc. 2067, 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2067-06>.
- Creutzig, F., Javaid, A., Soomauroo, Z., Lohrey, S., Milojevic-Dupont, N., Ramakrishnan, A., Sethi, M., Liu, L., Niamir, L., Bren d'Amour, C., Weddige, U., Lenzi, D., Kowarsch, M., Arndt, L., Baumann, L., Betzien, J., Fonkwa, L., Huber, B., Mendez, E., Misiou, A., Pearce, C., Radman, P., Skaloud, P., and Zausch, J. M. 2020. Fair street space allocation: ethical principles and empirical insights. *Transport Reviews*. 40, 711–733. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2020.1762795>.
- Executive Order 13985. 2021. Advancing Racial Equity and Support for Underserved Communities through the Federal Government <https://www.presidency.ucsb.edu/documents/executive-order-13985-advancing-racial-equity-and-support-for-underserved-communities>.
- Executive Order 13988. 2021. Preventing and combating discrimination on the basis of gender identity or sexual orientation <https://www.presidency.ucsb.edu/documents/executive-order-13988-preventing-and-combating-discrimination-the-basis-gender-identity-or>.
- Executive Order 14035. 2021. Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in the Federal Workforce <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2021/06/30/2021-14127/diversity-equity-inclusion-and-accessibility-in-the-federal-workforce>.
- Hasselberg, M. 2001. Socioeconomic differences in road traffic injuries during childhood and youth: a closer look at different kinds of road user. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*. 55, 858–862. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.55.12.858>.
- Levinson, D. 2010. Equity Effects of Road Pricing: A Review. *Transport Reviews*. 30, 33–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441640903189304>.
- Litman, T. A. 2021. Evaluating Transportation Equity: Guidance for Incorporating Distributional Impacts in Transport Planning. *Victoria Transport Policy Institute*.
- Motor Vehicle: Age Group Comparisons. Injury Facts, Available at <https://injuryfacts.nsc.org/motor-vehicle/overview/age-group-comparisons/>.
- NDOT GeoHub 2023. Available at <https://geohub-ndot.hub.arcgis.com/>.
- Palmateer, C., and Levinson, D. M. 2017. Justice, Exclusion, and Equity: An Analysis of 48 U.S. Metropolitan Areas.

Raifman, M. A., and Choma, E. F. 2022. Disparities in Activity and Traffic Fatalities by Race/Ethnicity. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*. 63, 160–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2022.03.012>.

Roy, A., and Law, M. 2022. Examining spatial disparities in electric vehicle charging station placements using machine learning. *Sustainable Cities and Society*. 83, 103978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.103978>.

Ryan, A., Christofa, E., Barchers, C., and Knodler, M. 2021. The relationship between municipal highway expenditures and socio-demographic status: Are safety investments equitably distributed? *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*. 9, 100321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100321>.

Sagar, S., Stamatiadis, N., and Stromberg, A. 2021. Effect of Socioeconomic and Demographic Factors on Crash Occurrence. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*. 2675, 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981211027887>.

Talen, E. 1998. Visualizing Fairness: Equity Maps for Planners. *Journal of the American Planning Association*. 64, 22–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944369808975954>.

U.S. Census Bureau 2018. Understanding and using American Community Survey data: What all data users need to know. US Department of Commerce, Economics and Statistics Administration, US Census Bureau.

U.S. Department of Transportation 2022. Research, Development, and Technology Strategic Plan Fiscal Year 2022-2026. Available at <https://www.transportation.gov/rdtstrategicplan>.

Van Dort, L., Guthrie, A., Fan, Y., and Baas, G. 2019. Advancing Transportation Equity: Research and Practice. Center for Transportation Studies, University of Minnesota.